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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Bo'lajak chet tili o'qituvchilarining innovatsion pedagogik kompetentligini rivojlantirish mexanizmi	10
<i>Mirzaraxonova Maftuna Ibroximjon qizi</i>	
Elementlarini integratsiya qilish: nazariy va amaliy yondashuv	13
<i>Ne'matov Karimjon Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida kitobxonlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari ...	19
<i>Mahmudova Shoira Shavkat qizi</i>	
O'zbek milliy musiqasi asosida talablarda estetik did va ijro madaniyatini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	25
<i>Gadoyeva Muborak Jumaqulovna</i>	
O'quvchilarning yozuv kompetensiyasini baholash mezonlarini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	30
<i>Abdurashidova Xafiza Abdurashidovna</i>	
Xurshid Do'stmuhammad qissalarida rivoyatchi strategiyasi.....	34
<i>Uzoqova Nargiza Yuldosh qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlashni shakllantirishda innovatsion texnologiyalarining ahamiyati	37
<i>Eshpulatov Shakir Nabiyevich, Ahrorova Ozoda Amriddinovna</i>	
"Xonada o'simliklarni o'stirish" intellekt xaritasi (Mind Map) yordamida o'quvchilarda ekologik tarbiya va ijodiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	41
<i>G'aniyev Abduqahhor Gadoyevich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda amaliy mashg'ulotlarning tashkiliy-pedagogik jihatlari.....	46
<i>Joldasov Ixtiyor Suyundikovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda iqtisodiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalari	50
<i>N. Asadov</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlashda kreativ kompetentlik va kasbiy muvaffaqiyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik mezonlari.....	53
<i>G. Xamidova</i>	
Gamifikatsiya elementlarining bakalavr talabalarini raqamli resurs yaratishga motivatsiyasiga ta'siri	56
<i>Maxkamova Dilshodaxon Xabibjon qizi</i>	
The Influence of Family Parenting Style on the Formation of Primary School Students' Personality	59
<i>Berdiyeva Mohloroyim Mirzohid qizi</i>	
Noto'liq oilalardagi onalarning tarbiyaviy uslublari va farzandlarining ijtimoiy-psixologik moslashuvi (O'zbekiston namunasida).....	64
<i>Ismoiljonov Ravshan Baxtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Raqamli pedagogika sharoitida interfaol ta'lim metodlari asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish.....	69
<i>Jumaniyozova Donoxon Olimboyevna, Bekmuratova Muhayyo Uralbayevna</i>	
Matematika ta'limida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning metodik asoslari.....	73
<i>Mirzayeva Shahlo, Qodirova Muattar Ilhom qizi, Rovshanova Yulduz Shovkat qizi</i>	

THE INFLUENCE OF FAMILY PARENTING STYLE ON THE FORMATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' PERSONALITY

Berdiyeva Mohloroyim Mirzohid qizi

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Annotatsiya: Oila bolada shaxs shakllanishining eng muhim ijtimoiy muhiti hisoblanadi. Mazkur tadqiqotda oilaviy tarbiya uslublarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari shaxsiy rivojlanishiga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Ayniqsa, oiladagi psixologik muhit, ota-ona va farzand o'rtasidagi munosabatlar hamda tarbiya usullarining bolaning xulq-atvori, hissiy holati va ijtimoiy moslashuviga ta'siri yoritilgan. Shuningdek, avtoritar, demokratik, liberal va befarq tarbiya uslublarining o'ziga xos jihatlari ilmiy manbalar asosida tavsiflangan. Ota-onaning qo'llab-quvvatlashi, nazorat darajasi va kutishlari bolalarda mustaqillik, mas'uliyat, o'zini anglash va o'quv motivatsiyasini shakllantirishdagi muhim omil sifatida baholangan. Tadqiqot natijalari sog'lom oilaviy muhit bolaning har tomonlama barkamol shaxs sifatida rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oilaviy tarbiya usublari, oilaviy muhit, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari, shaxs rivojlanishi, avtoritar uslub, demokratik uslub, liberal uslub, befarq uslub, motivatsiya, ijtimoiy moslashuv.

Abstract: The family serves as the primary social environment in the formation of a child's personality. This study examines the influence of family parenting styles on the personal development of primary school students. Particular attention is paid to the psychological climate within the family, parent-child relationships, and the impact of parenting methods on children's behavior, emotional well-being, and social adaptation. The characteristics of authoritarian, democratic, liberal, and indifferent parenting styles are analyzed on the basis of scientific literature. The study also highlights the importance of parental support, the level of control, and expectations in developing independence, responsibility, self-awareness, and learning motivation in children. The findings indicate that a supportive family environment plays a significant role in fostering the comprehensive development of a well-rounded personality.

Key words: parenting styles, family environment, primary school students, personality development, authoritarian style, democratic style, liberal style, indifferent style, motivation, social adaptation.

Аннотация: Семья является важнейшей социальной средой формирования личности ребёнка. В данном исследовании анализируется влияние стилей семейного воспитания на личностное развитие учащихся начальных классов. Особое внимание уделено психологическому климату в семье, взаимоотношениям между родителями и детьми, а также воздействию методов воспитания на поведение ребёнка, его эмоциональное состояние и социальную адаптацию. На основе научных источников охарактеризованы особенности авторитарного, демократического, либерального и безразличного стилей воспитания. Подчёркивается значимость родительской поддержки, уровня контроля и ожиданий в формировании у детей самостоятельности, ответственности, самосознания и учебной мотивации. Результаты исследования показывают, что благоприятная семейная среда играет важную роль в формировании гармонично развитой личности ребёнка.

Ключевые слова: стили семейного воспитания, семейная среда, учащиеся начальных классов, развитие личности, авторитарный стиль, демократический стиль, либеральный стиль, безразличный стиль, мотивация, социальная адаптация.

INTRODUCTION

A child's development begins within the family. Here, the factors influencing the child can be divided into two categories: the environment and parental influence. Through perceiving the surrounding world, the child learns what is good and what is bad, how to act in specific situations, and how to respond to particular events. Parents should help their children learn all of this, support the development of willpower, the ability to make the right choices even when it is difficult, and adherence to moral principles under any circumstances.

The primary influence of parents lies in their example – that is, in being role models. Young children always look up to their parents as models, imitate their actions, accept their views as consistently correct, and trust

them implicitly. The family is the child's primary and most important environment of socialization; the child acquires initial knowledge within the family, which serves as the foundation for personal development. It is within the family that values, norms of behavior, and patterns of interpersonal relationships are formed [1].

Initially, the child acts based on family values; later, as a result of participation in broader social life, personal values are formed. In the context of updated educational standards, special attention is being paid to the personal outcomes of primary school students. This increases the importance of analyzing family upbringing factors as a key resource in shaping stable personal qualities [1, p. 19]. This is because the effectiveness of a child's learning activities directly depends on the family environment, the support provided, and the parenting style applied.

Primary school age is considered a sensitive period for the development of voluntary behavior, the growth of reflection (self-analysis), the formation of adequate self-esteem, and the emergence of learning motivation [5, p. 62]. Therefore, the nature of relationships within the family during this period is of decisive importance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A substantial body of theoretical and empirical research in both local and international psychology confirms that parenting style has a direct impact on the characteristics of a child's personality development [2, p. 51]. When family upbringing is properly structured, the likelihood of developmental problems in children is considerably reduced. In examining the influence of parenting styles on child development, it is essential first to understand their nature and typology. Issues related to family dynamics, relationships, and parenting styles have attracted the attention of numerous scholars. Various typologies of parenting styles have been proposed within different theoretical frameworks, and in contemporary psychology, D. Baumrind's classification of parenting styles is regarded as one of the most influential and widely recognized.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is based on the analysis of scientific literature related to family parenting styles and the personality development of primary school students. Data were collected through the examination of psychological, pedagogical, and sociological sources, including scholarly articles, monographs, and empirical studies conducted by local and foreign researchers. Comparative and descriptive analysis methods were applied to identify the characteristics and influence of authoritarian, democratic, liberal, and neglectful parenting styles on children's emotional, social, and cognitive development. In addition, the study used content analysis to interpret theoretical findings and evaluate the relationship between family environment, parental attitudes, and the formation of children's personal qualities, learning motivation, and social adaptation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

D. Baumrind, based on the relationships between parents and children within the family, distinguishes the following parenting styles [11]:

1. **Authoritarian parenting style** – in this type of family, parents are highly strict and demand unquestioning obedience from their children. In such families, the child's opinions are usually not taken into account, and open discussion is not encouraged. Although parents maintain constant interaction with the child, they do not allow autonomy; children are required to comply directly with instructions and commands. Children raised in such an environment tend to develop as withdrawn, shy, insecure, fearful, irritable, and sometimes emotionally unstable, and they often become dependent on their parents. This parenting style frequently leads to the formation of external motivation, increased anxiety, and a strong dependence on adult evaluation [6, p. 74]. Research indicates that girls raised under this style may become passive and dependent, whereas boys may develop disobedient or aggressive patterns of behavior.
2. **Liberal parenting style** – in this type of family, parents consider their children as equals and grant them a high level of freedom. Such parents value their children and believe that they should independently acquire social skills and, in general, knowledge about the world. In these families, there are usually no clearly defined rules or restrictions. Prohibitions are rarely imposed, and parental control over the child's behavior is minimal; guidance and direction are also often lacking. In this context, expectations and demands regarding the outcomes of the child's activities are not clearly established. The absence of clear requirements and boundaries may lead to a decline in self-regulation and responsibility [6, p. 79]. As a result of this parenting style, the child may develop into an individual characterized by infantilism, impulsive behavior, avoidance of responsibility, heightened anxiety, and fear of activity and achievement.

3. **Indifferent (neglectful) parenting style** – in this type of family, the upbringing of the child is not considered particularly important by the parents. Such parents are usually preoccupied with their own work and personal problems, leaving the child to deal with their difficulties independently. Parents do not monitor the child's activities, provide little or no support, and show minimal interest in the child's life. As a result, a child raised in such a family environment may develop feelings of loneliness and worthlessness.
4. **Democratic parenting style** – this style is considered by many scholars to be the most balanced approach. In this context, parents establish rules for the child, but they are not overly rigid; the child's opinions are respected and taken into account. Individual psychological characteristics are also considered. This style combines emotional support, respect for the child's individuality, and reasonable demands [2, p. 56]. As a result, a child raised in such an environment develops into an individual who can express their thoughts freely, understands their parents, and is well-mannered, responsible, and proactive, as well as respectful and appreciative of both themselves and others. As the child grows older, they tend to apply the same parenting style with their own children, and this approach is often transmitted across generations.

Another classification of family relationships is also distinguished, which is based on the distance between parents and the child. According to this approach, there are three styles of family interaction: optimal distance, reduced distance, and increased distance [12].

1. **Optimal distance** – this style is based on parents' respectful attitude toward their children, which, in turn, fosters respect from children toward their parents. In such families, parents view their children as independent individuals and value their opinions. When guiding the child's activities, the child's interests are given priority. Influence is exercised not through strict demands or rigid commands, but through helping the child understand the necessity of appropriate behavior and cooperation. Relationships are built on the principles of collaboration and mutual understanding. Parents show genuine interest and actively participate in all aspects of their child's life; however, they do not impose their views. Instead, they invite the child to engage in shared activities, becoming involved only if the child accepts the invitation.
2. **Reduced distance** – this communication style is characterized by excessive protection of the child, strict control, and restriction of freedom. Parents make all decisions themselves and, regardless of the child's age, tend to perceive them as too young, inexperienced, incapable, and so on. They impose their own views and beliefs on the child and choose their social circle, activities, and interests without the child's participation. Children raised in such families grow up lacking initiative, weak-willed, and unable to act independently. As adults, these individuals often seek a partner who can act as a substitute for a parent, someone who is able to take care of them and provide guidance.
3. **Increased distance** – this style is characterized by parents' deliberate or forced emotional and physical distancing from their children. Parents spend little time with their children and are concerned mainly with their basic well-being. Minimal communication leads to a loss of interest in the child's life; their desires, inclinations, and opinions are not taken into account. As a result, the child may become rude, emotionally detached, and indifferent.

From the perspective of the cultural-historical approach, personality development occurs in the process of joint activity with adults, primarily with parents [7, p. 112]. The initial collective relationships are formed within the family. The child observes, analyzes, and learns from the interactions between parents, as well as their interactions with others, and later demonstrates what has been learned in their own activities. If the family environment is unfavorable, this is reflected in the child's behavior and activities. Through the system of family interpersonal relationships, the child acquires social roles, methods of conflict resolution, and norms of emotional expression [4, p. 35]. According to research, children who frequently witness conflicts within the family tend to develop either a high level of conflict-proneness or a tendency to avoid conflicts.

An emotional environment within the family, characterized by acceptance and support of the child, contributes to the formation of a positive "self-concept" (a system of self-awareness and self-esteem) [5, p. 68]. This is because, in such families, opinions are listened to, respected, and taken into consideration. As a result, the child develops into an individual who is able to express their personal opinion openly, fulfill responsibilities, and assert their rights. If the child's opinion is not heard or taken into account within the family, they may grow up being afraid or ashamed to express their thoughts in later activities as well. Consequently, due to a low level of critical thinking, the child may become dependent on the opinions of others. Constant criticism and devaluation of the child's achievements may reinforce feelings of failure and insecurity [6, p. 83].

During early school age, when learning is the leading activity, parents' attitudes toward a child's successes and failures play a decisive role in the formation of intrinsic learning motivation [3, p. 137]. That is, if a child is supported and encouraged by parents, their intrinsic motivation toward learning increases significantly. In

this case, intrinsic motivation is strengthened by external motivation. However, if the child's performance is constantly criticized or evaluated only in terms of grades, they may begin to perceive learning as an obligation. As a result, intrinsic motivation may decrease, and the child's activity becomes driven solely by external motivation. This, in turn, usually leads to lower effectiveness in learning activities.

In contemporary research, parental attitudes and expectations are considered to be of particular importance, as they determine the nature of demands placed on the child and the ways in which their activity is supported [2, p. 60]. If parents expect their child to achieve only high grades, they tend to apply stricter methods. If parents allow the child to make mistakes and support their independent activity, the child becomes freer, is not afraid of engaging in new activities, and acts more actively. However, some parents expect perfection from their children and punish any incorrect behavior. As a result, the child may develop into a fearful individual who avoids new activities and is unable to think freely.

Excessively high expectations, in the absence of emotional support, may lead to perfectionist tendencies and a fear of making mistakes in primary school children [6, p. 91]. The child constantly fears making mistakes and, even under pressure, attempts to complete tasks perfectly. Sometimes, children are assigned tasks that exceed their capabilities and are expected to complete them, even though they are unable to do so despite their efforts. This may lead to a decrease in self-confidence. If parents assign tasks that are within the child's abilities and provide support, the child is more likely to develop into a confident and well-adjusted individual. In other words, when realistic and adequate expectations are combined with recognition of the child's efforts, they promote the development of persistence, independence, and responsibility [5, p. 73].

Thus, the formation of a primary school student's personality largely depends on the balance between parental support and strictness in family upbringing [4, p. 41]. If both are maintained at an appropriate level, the expected outcomes can be achieved.

One of the contemporary global issues, namely the culture of internet use, is also shaped within the family. In the context of digitalization and children's active engagement in the information environment, the family becomes the main institution regulating a child's media behavior. It forms the foundations of digital literacy and the culture of technology use [8, p. 22]. At present, the proportion of individuals using the internet inappropriately is quite high, which is often the result of a lack of attention within the family and parental indifference toward the child. However, it is precisely within the family that children should be taught how to use technology correctly, how to manage their time spent online, and how to distinguish between useful and harmful content.

First of all, parents should limit their child's internet usage time while also regulating their own use of digital devices. Since a child learns by observing their parents, if parents spend most of their time on mobile phones, the child will inevitably imitate this behavior and spend most of their time on devices as well. Parents' attitudes toward digital devices, daily routines, and shared activities influence not only the child's cognitive development but also their volitional qualities, communication skills, and emotional stability [8, p. 29].

Modern research emphasizes that joint discussion of media content and parental involvement in a child's educational activities increase children's cognitive interest and contribute to the development of critical thinking [3, p. 142]. As a result, the child does not merely perceive the information they see or hear passively, but instead engages in analytical thinking and evaluates it critically.

As a child develops, they are exposed to a complex influence from the family. Analysis of scientific literature shows that the influence of family upbringing on the formation of a primary school student's personality is systematic in nature and is carried out through a combination of emotional, cognitive, and behavioral factors [1, p. 24]. As a result, through affection and support, the child develops self-confidence; through explanation and learning, they develop thinking and problem-solving abilities; and through established rules and expectations, behavioral norms are formed.

As the child develops, they interact with family members, and through this process, the family provides the child with their first experience of social interaction. Affection and support from family members foster a basic sense of trust toward the world. Constructive feedback from close relatives helps form the foundations of moral behavior and attitudes toward learning activities [7, p. 118]. In other words, the family serves as the child's first school of life, where initial experience is formed. According to literature analysis, it is precisely within the system of family relationships that the fundamental foundations of a child's personality are formed, which determine their success in both educational and social spheres.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the analysis of conducted research shows that the formation of a primary school student's personality is a process that is largely and directly dependent on the family environment and parental parenting style. The family serves as the primary socialization environment for the child, in which behavioral norms, value systems, experience of social relationships, and the foundations of self-awareness are formed.

According to the reviewed research findings, democratic parenting and emotionally supportive parenting styles contribute to the development of positive personal qualities in children, such as independence, responsibility, self-confidence, and social activity. In contrast, authoritarian, liberal, neglectful, or overly controlling parenting styles may lead to psychological imbalances in a child's development, such as a lack of initiative or emotional instability.

Furthermore, early school age is a sensitive period in personality development, during which parental role modeling, support, and the integration of reasonable demands with emotional warmth are of particular importance. In modern conditions, the family's regulation of the digital environment and the formation of media culture have also become significant factors in a child's personality development.

Overall, the formation of a well-rounded personality in a child is closely linked to the family upbringing system, parental attitudes, and pedagogical approaches, and the family remains the fundamental foundation of personality development.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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